

Hemisection-Substitute of Extraction: A Case Report

Praveen Kumar, Arun Verma, Shobhit Pratap Singh, Jasalok

Received on: 05 July, 2024; Accepted on: 05 August 2024; Published on: 14-09-2024

¹PGStudent,
Department of Conservative
Dentistry and Endodontics,
Chandra Dental College and
Hospital, Barabanki

²Professor and Head
Department of Conservative
Dentistry and Endodontics,
Chandra Dental College and
Hospital, Barabanki

³Assistant professor,
Department of Conservative
Dentistry and Endodontics,
Chandra Dental College and
Hospital, Barabanki

⁴PGStudent,
Department of Conservative
Dentistry and Endodontics,
Chandra Dental College and
Hospital, Barabanki

Abstract

Hemisection is sectioning of multi-rooted teeth followed by removal of compromised root along with its associated crown portion and leaving the healthy root (with crown) intact. This treatment option can be considered when caries, resorption, perforation, or periodontal damage is restricted to one root while the other root is relatively healthy. The most critical factor determining the long-term success in such cases is the appropriate case selection. This case report describes a case of hemisection of a mandibular molar followed by adequate restoration in a young patient.

Keywords: Hemisection; Furcation defect; Mandibular Molar; Endodontic surgery

Introduction

Advanced dental therapeutic measures have provided opportunity to retain teeth that were once considered non restorable. Such therapeutic measures involve multi disciplinary approach. Hemisection is one such treatment modality involving principles of restorative dentistry, endodontics, periodontics, oral surgery and prosthodontics.¹

It is a procedure carried out in a multi rooted tooth where in one-half of the crown and the associated un restorable root is removed at the level of the furcation, while leaving the healthy portion of the crown and its associated root in function thus maintaining its integrity within the socket. The most critical in determining the long-term success in such cases is the appropriate case selection which involves a combined periodontal, endodontic and prosthodontic assessment².

Modern advances in all phases of dentistry have provided the opportunity for patients to maintain a functional dentition for lifetime. Many people would prefer to keep their natural teeth and this is a good thing for several reasons. First off it is your natural tooth. Secondly, the cost of replacing a tooth either with a bridge or dental implant can be expensive and they run the chance of failure. A hemisection can only be done on the molars, the wider flatter teeth at the back of your mouth; the other teeth in your mouth simply wouldn't have the stability needed after the procedure. A hemisection cannot be done on an upper molar for it has three roots. But an expert/specialist dentist still could divide an upper molar into three parts (sometimes referred to as trisection), or could remove one or two roots (root resection) In some situations, this may require crown lengthening of one or both parts of the tooth

and roots. In certain instances, guided tissue regeneration can be used for the bone to grow again in the bifurcation area so a dental implant can be placed at a later date. The guiding principle is the preservation of remaining tooth structure and restoration of the function. This case report describes a case in which hemisection was chosen as a treatment plan to retain the mesial root of mandibular right first molar and extraction of un-treatable distal half of the tooth³.

Case Report

A 28-year-old male patient reported with a chief complaint of broken tooth in lower right back teeth region. Patient gave the history of endodontic treatment with the same tooth 3 years back. On intra oral examination lower right mandibular 1st molar (tooth no. 46) was root canal treated with dislodged post endodontic restoration. The Distal half of the tooth was grossly decayed with caries involving the pulpal floor at furcation area.

Fig- 1 Preoperative Clinical View

How to cite this article: Dr. Praveen et al.:
Hemisection-Substitute of Extraction-A Case Report
HTAJOCD-2024

Access this article online

Website

www.healtalk.in

Quick Response Code

Radiographic Examination

Radiographic examination of the tooth revealed radio lucency at pulpal floor, grossly decayed distal half, completely obturated mesial canals and no obturation in distal canal.

Fig-2 Preoperative Radiographic View

The treatment plan was explained to the patient and his informed consent was obtained. Oral prophylaxis was done out before commencement of the treatment pro-cedure.

Armamentarium

Long, shank tapered fissure bur, extraction forcep, perio-steal elevator, saline to remove bony chips, finishing diamond point, tissue forceps, needle holder, bone curette, 4-0 mersilk suture material etc.

Fig-3 Armamentarium For Surgical Procedure

Procedure

The mesial and distal roots were sectioned at the level of the bifurcation area using long shank tapered fissure bur, a dental probe was passed through the vertical cut to check the separation of the tooth segments at furcation level and a radiograph was taken to confirm the complete separation (Fig-4).

Fig-4 Longitudinal Section of Mandibular 1st Molar

After completion of the sectioning, the distal root along with its coronal part was luxated with elevators. The distal half of the tooth was removed from the socket with an extraction forcep (Figure 5). The socket was irrigated adequately with normal saline to remove bony chips. A finishing diamond point was used to smoothen the distal surface of the mesial root and its coronal portion. The extraction socket was sutured with 4-0 mersilk suture material and covered with a periodontal dressing (Fig 6 and7).

Fig-5 Extracted Distal Segment of Mandibular 1st Molar

Fig-6 Post Operative Clinical View

Fig-7 Post Operative Radiograph

Patient was recalled after one week for evaluation. At this

visit clinical examination revealed no pain and inflammation was present at extracted site. Irrigation with betadine solution was done and sutures were removed.

At 1-month recall visit, patient was asymptomatic and healing was found to be satisfactory, crown preparation for porcelain fused to metal crown was done using mesial segment of mandibular first molar and second molar as abutments. Impression was made and die was fabricated. After that final prosthesis (crown) was placed (Fig 8 and 9).

Fig-8 Prepared Prosthesis on A Master Cast

Fig-9 Crown Cementation

Discussion

Hemisection also known as root amputation is a useful alternative procedure to save those multi-rooted teeth which have been indicated for extraction. It is a relatively simple, conservative, inexpensive treatment with good chances of success provided appropriate case selection has been done⁴

Weine⁵ has given an insight on the specific indications

where this procedure should be considered.

1. Severe vertical bone loss involving only one root of multi-rooted teeth.
2. Through and through furcation destruction.
3. Unfavourable proximity of roots of adjacent teeth, preventing adequate hygiene maintenance in proximal areas.
4. Severe root exposure due to dehiscence.
5. Prosthetic failure of abutments within a splint.
6. Perforation through the floor of the pulp chamber.
7. Vertical fracture of one root.

Apart from considering these factors patient's oral hygiene status, caries index and medical status should also be considered for hemisection procedure. Park et al. has also suggested that hemisection is a reliable treatment option for molars with questionable prognosis as it will maintain the teeth without detectable bone loss for a long-term period, provided that the patient has optimal oral hygiene⁶. Also, accessibility of root furcation for easy separation as well as good bone support for the remaining root should be assessed.⁷ In the present case there was complete furcation involvement and the mesial half of the tooth was sound. Thus considering these factors and patients financial constraint hemisection was chosen as the treatment of choice⁸. This case demonstrates hemisection as an alternative treatment to extraction of a whole tooth and salvation of healthy tooth structure^{9,10}.

Conclusion

Hemisection can be considered as a predictable treatment option for a hopeless tooth and with advancements in endodontics, periodontics and restorative dentistry, it has received further acceptance. The key is the meticulous case selection and the treatment goal is to try and maintain what is present for restoration of the function.

The prognosis for hemisection is the same as for routine endodontic procedures provided.

That case selection has been correct.

The endodontics has been performed adequately, and

The restoration is of an acceptable design relative to the occlusal and periodontal needs of the patient.

Root amputation and hemisection should be considered as another weapon in the arsenal of the dental surgeon, determined to retain and not remove the natural teeth. With recent refinements in endodontics, periodontics, and restorative dentistry. Hemisection has received acceptance as a conservative and dependable dental treatment and teeth so treated have endured the demands of function.

References

1. Arora A, Arya A, Singhal R K, Khatana R. Hemisection: A conservative approach. *Indian J Dent Sci* 2017; 9: 206-9.
2. Sharma S, Sharma R, Ahad A, Gupta ND, Mishra SK. Hemisection as a Conservative Management Of Grossly Carious Permanent Mandibular First Molar. *J Nat Sci Biol Med* 2018; 9(1): 97-99.
3. Green, E. N. (1986). Hemisection and root amputation. *The Journal of the American Dental Association*, 112(4), 511-518.
4. Mittal P, Prasad AB, Raisingani D, Amit, Mehta P, Soni D, Khurana D. Hemisection: A Savior for Hopeless Teeth. *J Mahatma Gandhi Univ Med Sci Tech* 2016; (1): 30-34.
5. Weine F S. *Endodontic Therapy*. 5th ed. St. Louis, USA: Mosby; 1996. p. 154-68.
6. Park J B. Hemisection of teeth with questionable prognosis. *J Int Acad Periodontol* 2009; 11(3), 214-19.
7. Haskell E W, Stanley H R. Vital hemisection of mandibular second molar. *J Am Dent Assoc* 1981; 102: 503-6.
8. Babaji P, Sihag T, Chaurasia VR, Senthinathan S. Hemisection: A conservative management of periodontally involved molar tooth in a

- young patient. J Nat Sci Biol Med 2015; 6(1): 253-5.
9. Yuh D Y, Lin F G, Fang W H, Chien W C, Chung C H, Mau L P, et al. The impact of medical institutions on the treatment decisions and outcome of root-resected molars: A retrospective claims analysis from a representative database. J Med Sci. 2014; 34: 1-8.
10. Carnevale G, Di Febo G, Tonelli M P, Marin C, Fuzzi M. A retrospective analysis of the periodontal-prosthetic treatment of molars with inter radicular lesions. Int J Periodontics Restorative Dent. 1991; 11: 189-205.

TRANSFORMATIONAL ALLIANCES
CO-CREATING PIONEERING UPGRADES

LM

feel the
difference

COLTENE
INDIA

Choose smart.

